

INTERPRETABLE DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION USING PCA AND DEEP UNDERCOMPLETE AUTOENCODERS FOR BIOMARKER DISCOVERY IN HEAD AND NECK SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA

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Abstract

Background:

Head and neck squamous cell cancer (HNSC) is one of the most common cancers worldwide, and gene expression analysis can help in identifying the key genes involved in its pathogenesis. However, the dimensionality and the complexity of the high throughput cancer datasets make it challenging to identify the most important genes. In this study, we applied principal component analysis (PCA) as a base method of dimension reduction and compared its results with our implemented deep under-complete autoencoder (DUAЕ) model. Furthermore, clustering analysis was applied to analyze the common trends in the reduced expression data produced by PCA and DUAЕ to identify the key genes involved in HNSC.

Method:

This study used a head and neck cancer gene expression dataset (TCGA-HNSC) from TCGA (The Cancer Genome Atlas) and applied principal components analysis. We then built a deep under-complete autoencoder (DUAЕ) to reduce the genes. Next, we applied clustering analysis to identify groups of genes that exhibited similar expression patterns. Finally, we examined the reduced genes, identified through PCA and DUAЕ, through gene ontology analysis.

Result:

Our data analysis approach, DUAЕ, was able to significantly reduce the number of genes from 20,503 to 17,932 (12% reduction) as compared to PCA, which only reduced genes from 20,503 to 20,236. The clustering and gene ontology analysis showed that the refined genes were involved in crucial cellular processes such as signal transduction, and gene regulation pathways that may be crucial for HNSC oncogenesis.

Conclusion:

Our study highlights the potential of DUAЕ as a dimension reduction technique, which coupled with gene expression analysis can be used to identify the most significant genes associated with HNSC oncogenesis. These findings provide a stepping stone for future investigations aimed at uncovering the underlying molecular mechanisms of this disease.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a major global health challenge, and despite advancements in diagnosis and treatments, mortality associated with several

cancer types remains high [1]. For example seventh leading cause of cancer, head, and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC), has an annual mortality rate of 40–50%. The key risk factors for HNSCC include using tobacco and

alcohol, as well as infection with the human papillomavirus (HPV), which has been shown to affect prognosis [2-4].

Current cancer research heavily relies on gene expression analysis of cancer types to identify cancer-associated pathways or changes between cancer subtypes, etc. [5]. Expression profiles from cancerous cells and normal cells are comparatively analyzed to examine the activity of genes (either similar or different) in both groups. The key goal of such analyses is often to identify candidate/biomarker genes with significant diagnostic and/or prognostic value [6-8]. Much of the research on identifying differentially expressed genes has concentrated on the most significant changes, which may preclude recognition of subtler patterns in the data [9-15]. However, in-depth research analysis of such data is quite difficult due to their size and diversity. A solution to handle this problem, and make biological data more meaningful can be achieved by mathematical modeling approaches with biological data [16].

The rapid advancement in machine learning and deep learning techniques has opened up new possibilities for improved computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) of complex data patterns [17 - 19]. Deep learning, a sub-class of machine learning algorithms, utilizes multiple layers of artificial neurons to learn intricate representations of data through backpropagation [20 - 27]. Principal component analysis (PCA) is a traditional machine learning method for dimensionality reduction that performs well on linearly dependent data but struggles with nonlinear structures [28 - 30]. To address this limitation, autoencoder, an unsupervised deep learning system, is particularly effective in handling nonlinear data. By employing non-linear transformations and a bottleneck layer, the autoencoder reconstructs the original input while capturing informative characteristics in the data. These characteristics in the bottleneck layer can serve as additional representations of the input data, enabling enhanced analysis and interpretation [27], [31]. Previous studies have employed various traditional methods for reducing the dimensionality of gene expression datasets, such as linear discriminant analysis (LDA), independent component analysis (ICA), factor

analysis (FA), and principal component analysis (PCA). However, these methods have limitations in capturing the intricate relationships among variables in high-dimensional gene expression data. LDA is restricted to linear relationships, ICA may not provide a unique or stable separation of sources, and FA assumes linear relationships between observed variables and latent factors, which may not be true for gene expression datasets [32 - 34]. Other dimensionality reduction techniques like t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) and random forest have their limitations, such as sensitivity to parameter choice and difficulty in handling missing data or complex gene relationships [35, 36]. Similarly, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) may not be suitable for datasets with missing values and may not effectively capture nonlinear gene relationships [37]. Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF), another popular method, may struggle with complex gene relationships and sensitivity to parameter selection [38].

Therefore, there is a need for more sophisticated methods that can handle the nonlinear relationships and interactions among genes in gene expression datasets. This is where deep learning methods such as autoencoders can be particularly useful, as they can learn a more meaningful and compact representation of the input data by encoding it in a lower-dimensional space and then decoding it back into the original high-dimensional space, capturing the nonlinear relationships and interactions in the data [39, 40]. Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of autoencoder models in reducing the dimensionality of gene expression datasets [40 - 43]. However, such studies have also identified some limitations of autoencoder models, such as the potential for overfitting and difficulty in selecting appropriate hyperparameters.

Our study aims to overcome these limitations by implementing a deep under-complete autoencoder model, along with clustering analysis, and gene ontology analysis, to capture the complex relationships and nonlinear interactions among genes in high-dimensional gene expression datasets, and identify the most significant genes involved in HNSCC pathogenesis.

Methods

Data Collection and Dataset Structure

The Head and Neck Squamous Cell Cancer (HNSCC) gene expression data used in this study was obtained from the TCGA database using the RTCGA package in R [44]. The R TCGA dataset is a publicly available database that provides gene expression data for various types of cancers, including head and neck cancer. The dataset was collected through a combination of experimental methods, including RNA sequencing and microarray analysis. The dataset included expression profiles of 566 samples and 20,503 genes. The gene expression data was a matrix of log-transformed values of each gene, where rows (x_{i*}) correspond to samples obtained from patients and columns (x_{*j}) represent the genes. The elements x_{ij} of the matrix, X represents the log-transformed expression value of the gene in the patient sample.

Preprocessing of Dataset

Prior to dimensionality reduction and clustering analysis, the dataset was preprocessed by standardizing the gene expression values using z-score normalization. This ensures that all genes are on the same scale and have equal weight in the analysis.

Where,

C_x , is the number of components extracted,

b_{xp} , is the weight for the observed gene p as used in creating component x ,

X_p , is the score on the observed gene.

The normalization was calculated as:

$$s_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - \mu}{\sigma}$$

where s_{ij} is the normalized gene expression value of the i^{th} gene for a particular sample, x_{ij} is the original gene expression value of the i^{th} gene, μ is the overall mean of the HNSCC gene expression data, and σ is the standard deviation of the gene expression data.

Building of PCA Model

To perform dimensionality reduction, a standard PCA model was built using the factoextra package in R [45]. This package provides robust and widely used methods for dimensionality reduction and clustering analysis. In this study, PCA was used as the base dimensionality reduction technique to extract meaningful components from HNSCC gene expression data. The entire gene expression data was passed to the PCA model which as a result produced the resultant component by calculating the variance of each gene (Figure 1). The mathematical representation of the model is given as:

$$C_x = b_{xp}(X_p) + \dots + b_{xn}(X_n)$$

Figure 1. The principal component analysis (PCA) model for HNSCC data. The dataset was added to the PCA model, which calculated the variance of the data and produced the resulting components shown in the figure. The x-axis represents the count of genes, and the y-axis represents the calculated variance of

each gene. The principal components were produced in output based on the variance calculated for each gene. The first principal component had the highest variance as compared to the last component.

To select the components that best represented the HNSCC gene expression data, two approaches were used: cumulative percent variance and the Scree test. In cumulative percent variance, a threshold value of 95% was set, based on the cumulative value of the variance of each component, and components till 95% cumulative variance percent were selected. In the Scree test, the Eigenvalues were plotted, and breaks (decay in the values) in the graph were identified. The last value of the last break was selected, i.e., around 408, and the remaining components were ignored.

Building of Deep Under-complete Autoencoder

For the implementation of the autoencoder model, H2O 3 was used in anaconda python [46, 47]. H2O 3 is a powerful machine-learning platform that provides a range of tools for data analysis and modeling. A deep under-complete autoencoder was implemented using a neural network with three deep layers (Figure 2). The first layer had 500 neurons, the second layer had 200 neurons, and the third layer had 100 neurons. The rectifier activation function was used for all the neurons in the network. The model was trained for 100 epochs with a learning rate of $1e-5$ and an input dropout ratio of 0.2. The model was designed to be sparse, which means that only a few neurons in each layer were active at any given time.

Figure 2. A deep under-complete autoencoder for the HNSCC dataset. The model consists of 3 deep layers with 500,200,100 neurons in each layer respectively. The rectifier activation function was used with a dropout of 0.2.

The mathematical representation of the model can be given as:

Let X be the input dataset of size $N \times D$, where N is the number of samples and D is the number of features. The model can be represented as a composition of two functions: an encoder function f and a decoder function g . The

encoder function maps the input data to a hidden representation z , while the decoder function maps the hidden representation back to the original input space.

The encoder function f can be represented as [48, 49]:

$$z = f(X) = h(W_1 X + b_1)$$

where h is the rectifier activation function, W_1 is the weight matrix connecting the input layer to the first hidden layer, and b_1 is the bias vector for the first hidden layer.

The decoder function g can be represented as [48, 49]:

$$X' = g(z) = h(W_2 z + b_2)$$

where W_2 is the weight matrix connecting the hidden layer to the output layer, and b_2 is the bias vector for the output layer.

The objective of the autoencoder model is to minimize the reconstruction error between the input and the output, which is given by the mean squared error (MSE) loss function [48, 49]:

$$L(X, X') = ||X - X'||^2$$

To encourage sparsity in the hidden representation z , an additional regularization term is added to the loss function, which penalizes the activation of too many neurons in each layer. This is done using an L1 regularization term [48, 49]:

$$L1 = \lambda ||z||_1$$

Where λ is the regularization parameter.

DUAE learns to encode the high-dimensional gene expression data into a lower-dimensional representation by minimizing the reconstruction error between the input and the output. In this process, the DUAE identifies and removes the noise and irrelevant information from the data, leading to a reduced set of genes that capture the essential patterns and variations in the data. Therefore, the DUAE reduces the genes based on their contribution to the overall variability in the gene expression data, rather than on any preconceived notions about their functional relevance.

Clustering Analysis

After dimensionality reduction using both PCA and DUAE, clustering analysis was performed on each of the reduced data produced by the two techniques using the k-means algorithm in the factoextra package. Clustering analysis is a powerful technique used to group similar gene expression profiles [50], while the K-means algorithm is a widely used unsupervised clustering algorithm that partitions the data into K clusters, where K is the number of clusters

defined by the user. The algorithm iteratively assigns data points to the nearest cluster centroid and updates the centroid based on the mean of the assigned data points until convergence [50, 51]. To identify the optimal number of clusters, we used two widely used metrics: the elbow method and silhouette score [51, 52]. The quality of the resulting clusters was evaluated using within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS), and silhouette score. WCSS measures the sum of squared distances of each data point to its assigned centroid and indicates how compact the clusters are, while the silhouette score measures the similarity of data points within a cluster and dissimilarity to points in other clusters [51, 52].

Gene-Ontology Analysis

Gene ontology analysis was performed to further understand the biological functions and activities of the important variables produced by the PCA and DUAE. The differentially expressed genes identified by both PCA and DUAE were input into the Gene Ontology (GO) Consortium database (<http://www.geneontology.org/>) to obtain information on their molecular functions, biological processes, and cellular components. GO enrichment analysis was performed using the Gene Ontology Enrichment Analysis web tool (<http://geneontology.org/>). The enriched GO terms were identified using a p-value cutoff of <0.05 and were further filtered using a false discovery rate (FDR) of <0.05 .

Results:

Principal Component Analysis

The input data for PCA consisted of 20503 genes, which was reduced to 20236 genes after filtering out missing values. The PCA model produced a total of 408 components. The top 10 variance values of components are shown in Table 1. The first component had the highest Eigenvalue among all components, representing the maximum variance reserved in this component. The proportion of variance in each Eigenvalue is shown in the second column of Table 1.

Table 1. Top 10 components produced by principal component analysis for HNSCC data.

	eigenvalue	Variance percent	Cumulative variance percent
Dim.1	1692.972248	8.366140779	8.366140779
Dim.2	1247.703458	6.165761308	14.53190209
Dim.3	917.5207241	4.534101226	19.06600331
Dim.4	754.5783111	3.728890646	22.79489396
Dim.5	621.8320863	3.072900209	25.86779417
Dim.6	470.4059747	2.324599598	28.19239377
Dim.7	409.1398211	2.021841377	30.21423514
Dim.8	327.1762824	1.616803135	31.83103828
Dim.9	310.0623591	1.532231464	33.36326974
Dim.10	267.0233555	1.319546133	34.68281588

Additionally, the first principal component accounted for the largest amount of variance in the data, with a cumulative variance ratio of approximately 23% (Figure 3). In the next step, we examined the threshold for variances to be included in the analysis, as more principal components are included in the analysis, the

cumulative variance ratio also increases until a threshold is achieved. In our study, the first 408 principal components appeared to capture over 95% of the variance in the data (Figure 3, red line), suggesting that including additional components would not significantly increase the amount of variance explained.

Figure 3. Cumulative variance as explained by principal components. The figure shows the percentage of variance explained cumulatively by the first 10 principal components extracted from the dataset. The horizontal axis represents the number of principal components, while the vertical axis represents the percentage of variance explained. The red line indicates the 95% threshold for cumulative variance explained.

The scree plot analysis showed that the eigenvalues started high and decreased rapidly for the first few components. The first component had the highest eigenvalue, which was around 1700, and the eigenvalues decreased gradually for the next several components. There was a noticeable inflection point at around the 408th component, where the eigenvalues started to plateau and decrease much more slowly. This

inflection point suggested that the first 408 components were the most important ones and that adding additional components beyond that point had little effect on the variance in the data. Based on this scree plot, we can have concluded that the first 408 principal components should be retained in the PCA analysis for this dataset, which explains around 95% of the variance in the data.

Figure 4: Scree plot for the principal component analysis. Scree plot showing the eigenvalues of principal components obtained from a principal component analysis (PCA) of the data. The x-axis represents the number of principal components, and the y-axis shows the corresponding eigenvalues. The elbow point at component 408 indicated the optimal number of principal components to retain for the analysis. The cumulative variance explained by the retained components was 95%.

Deep Under-Complete Autoencoder (DUAЕ)

We also employed a deep under-complete autoencoder to reduce the dimensionality of our gene expression data. Out of 20503 genes, 17932 genes were retained after the DUAЕ reduction. The DUAЕ reduced the genes based on their expression patterns in the given dataset. The mean squared error (MSE) and root mean squared error (RMSE) were calculated to evaluate the performance of the DUAЕ. The MSE and RMSE values were found to be 0.029

and 0.171, respectively, indicating a good fit of the model to the data.

The MSE plot showed that the model's performance improved over time, as the MSE loss decreased with each epoch (Figure 5). This indicated that the model was learning to better represent the input data in a lower-dimensional space through the process of dimensionality reduction. The training process appeared to stabilize around epoch 200, after which the reduction in MSE loss was less pronounced.

Figure 5. The plot of Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss for the autoencoder model during training and validation. The training and validation loss values are shown on the y-axis, and the number of epochs is shown on the x-axis. The blue line represents the training loss, and the orange line represents the validation loss. The training and validation loss initially decreased together. The training process appeared to stabilize around epoch 200, after which the reduction in MSE loss was less pronounced.

Similarly, the RMSE plot showed a decreased trend of reconstruction error as the number of epochs increased (Figure 6), indicating that the DUAE model was learning to better represent the input data with each epoch of training. The initial high error was expected as the model was still in the learning phase, but as it continued to train, the error decreased. The graph also

showed some fluctuations in the reconstruction error, which is common during the training process due to the stochastic nature of the optimization algorithm. However, overall, the trend was towards lower error and better performance of the DUAE model as the training progresses.

Figure 6. Training and validation Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) for a deep under-complete autoencoder model. The plot shows the RMSE loss for both the training and validation sets during the training process of the autoencoder model. The x-axis represents the number of epochs, while the y-axis represents the RMSE value. The blue line represents the RMSE loss for the training set, while the orange line represents the RMSE loss for the validation set. The training and validation RMSE losses started to converge around epoch 100, indicating that the model had reached a stable state.

Clustering Analysis

Clustering analysis was performed on the reduced set of genes obtained from the PCA and DUAE. The elbow and silhouette methods were used to determine the optimal number of clusters, which were found to be 5 and 8, respectively (Figures 7 and 8).

In our plots, the elbow points were located at k=5 (PCA) and k=8 (DUAE), indicating that these were the optimal number of clusters for our dataset. Beyond k=5 and 8, the reduction in WCSS became less pronounced, suggesting that additional clusters did not provide significant improvement in cluster quality.

Figure 7. Elbow Plot for k-means clustering algorithm plotted for the reduced set of genes produced by PCA. Elbow plot showing the total within-cluster sum of squares (WSS) for different values of k in K-means clustering. The optimal number of clusters can be determined by selecting the point where the

rate of decrease in WSS starts to level off (the "elbow" of the curve), which in this case appeared to be at $k=5$.

Figure 8. Elbow Plot for k-means clustering algorithm applied on the reduced set of genes from DUAE. Elbow plot showing the total within-cluster sum of squares (WSS) for different values of k in K-means clustering. The optimal number of clusters can be determined by selecting the point where the rate of decrease in WSS starts to level off (the "elbow" of the curve), which in this case appeared to be at $k=8$.

A k-means clustering algorithm was then applied to these genes, also resulting in the formation of 5 and 8 distinct clusters for PCA and DUAE respectively (Figures 9 and 10). The clustering

algorithm was able to accurately group the data points into their respective clusters, demonstrating the effectiveness of the approach in identifying patterns in the data.

Figure 9. Clustering of the reduced set of genes produced by PCA using the k-means algorithm. The scatter plot shows the distribution of data points in two-dimensional space. The data points are color-coded to represent the cluster assignment generated by the k-means clustering algorithm with $k=5$. The x-axis and y-axis represent the first and second principal components, respectively.

Figure 10. Clustering of the DUAE reduced genes set using the k-means algorithm. The scatter plot shows the distribution of data points in two-dimensional space. The data points are color-coded to represent the cluster assignment generated by the k-means clustering algorithm with k=8. The x-axis and y-axis represent the first and second principal components, respectively.

The clusters were then analyzed to determine their functional significance using gene ontology (GO) analysis (Table 2). Overall, the clustering analysis based on the reduced set of genes from

PCA and DUAE identified distinct functional clusters of genes that were significantly enriched in different biological processes.

Table 2. GO analysis of clusters obtained from PCA and DUAE

Number of Clusters	Molecular Function of Genes from PCA	Molecular Function of Genes from DUAE
Cluster 1	Protein kinase inhibitor activity, structural constituent of the cytoskeleton, and protein binding activity	Metabolic processes, cellular processes, and developmental processes. Some of the molecular functions include catalytic activity, binding, and transporter activity, while some of the cellular components include membrane-bound organelles, intracellular organelles, and extracellular regions.
Cluster 2	Structural constituent of cytoskeleton	Signal transduction, such as protein kinase activity and receptor signaling, catalytic activity, protein binding, and metabolic functions
Cluster 3	Binding activities such as indanol dehydrogenase activity, insulin-like growth factor I binding, nitric-oxide synthase regulation, protein, ADP, signal receptor binding, protease binding such as enzyme binding, and calcium ion binding.	Regulation of blood pressure, response to hypoxia, positive regulation of cell migration, and cellular response to mechanical stimulus, regulation of cell proliferation, positive regulation

		of protein kinase B signaling, positive regulation of the apoptotic process, and regulation of protein localization to the plasma membrane, positive regulation of leukocyte chemotaxis, and positive regulation of cytokine production
Cluster 4	Platelet-derived growth factor binding, structural constituent of skin epidermis, inhibitor, and regulator activity	Metabolic processes, including oxidative phosphorylation and lipid metabolism
Cluster 5	Protein kinase activity such as catalytic, transferase, kinase activity, signal transduction, and binding activities.	DNA-binding functions, such as transcription factor activity and chromatin binding DNA repair, regulation of RNA splicing, RNA binding
Cluster 6	-	Catalytic activity, transport-related functions, such as ion transport and vesicle-mediated transport
Cluster 7	-	Neuron development, including axon guidance and synaptic transmission
Cluster 8	-	Protein processing and modification, blood vessel development, extracellular matrix organization, signal transduction, and binding activities

Gene-Ontology:

The reduced set of genes produced by PCA and DUAE were passed for gene ontology analysis. First, the reduced set of genes was annotated with gene ontology terms, and subsequently, gene ontology analysis was performed to determine the enrichment of specific gene ontology terms within the set of reduced genes. The gene ontology analysis helps interpret the results of the reduced gene set obtained through

PCA and DUAE techniques by providing functional annotations and insights into the biological significance of the identified genes. The results of the gene ontology (GO) analysis performed in this study are presented in Tables 3 and 4. The analysis identified genes with several molecular functions, such as protein domain-specific binding, phosphotransferase, kinase activity, enzyme regulation, etc., to be significantly enriched in the input gene set.

Table 3. Gene Ontology analysis of the reduced set of genes produced by principal component analysis

GO molecular function complete	Homo sapiens REFLIST (20589)	upload_1 (20236)	expected	over/under	fold Enrichment	raw P-value	FD R
protein domain-specific binding	666	637	523.15	1.22	+	3.06E-04	3.37 E-02
phosphotransferase activity, alcohol group as acceptor	687	655	539.65	1.21	+	3.33E-04	3.51 E-02
kinase activity	760	721	596.99	1.21	+	2.25E-04	2.65 E-02
enzyme binding	2092	1978	1643.30	1.20	+	4.13E-10	1.23 E-07
ATP binding	1491	1404	1171.21	1.20	+	4.31E-07	6.60 E-05
cytoskeletal protein binding	999	940	784.73	1.20	+	4.74E-05	6.30 E-03
identical protein binding	2169	2014	1703.79	1.18	+	1.02E-08	2.35 E-06
RNA binding	1674	1545	1314.95	1.17	+	1.77E-06	2.56 E-04
protein-containing complex binding	1304	1195	1024.31	1.17	+	7.27E-05	9.19 E-03
enzyme regulator activity	1332	1217	1046.31	1.16	+	8.46E-05	1.04 E-02
metal ion binding	4321	3904	3394.22	1.15	+	7.22E-13	2.61 E-10
catalytic activity, acting on a protein	2326	2076	1827.11	1.14	+	6.81E-06	9.57 E-04
hydrolase activity	2436	2150	1913.52	1.12	+	2.69E-05	3.68 E-03
DNA binding	2523	2187	1981.86	1.10	+	3.18E-04	3.42 E-02
Unclassified	2371	856	1862.46	.46	-	8.77E-102	2.22 E-98

G protein-coupled receptor activity	885	319	695.18	.46	-	3.60E-37	3.03E-34
antigen binding	124	39	97.40	.40	-	1.24E-07	2.23E-05
structural constituent of chromatin	63	8	49.49	.16	-	4.35E-09	1.10E-06
bitter taste receptor activity	22	1	17.28	.06	-	5.63E-05	7.30E-03
odorant binding	125	5	98.19	.05	-	1.70E-25	1.23E-22
olfactory receptor activity	441	17	346.41	.05	-	6.57E-88	8.31E-85

Table 4. Gene Ontology analysis of the reduced set of genes produced by the deep under-complete autoencoder

GO molecular function complete	Homo sapiens REFLIST (20589)	upload_1 (17932)	expected	over/under	fold Enrichment	raw P-value	FD R
ion binding (GO:0043167)	6088	5779	5302.35	+	1.09	1.79E-08	1.11E-05
metal ion binding (GO:0046872)	4292	4066	3738.12	+	1.09	1.44E-05	5.53E-03
cation binding (GO:0043169)	4383	4151	3817.38	+	1.09	1.19E-05	4.95E-03
organic cyclic compound binding (GO:0097159)	6054	5700	5272.73	+	1.08	4.23E-07	2.34E-04
heterocyclic compound binding (GO:1901363)	5983	5629	5210.9	+	1.08	6.90E-07	3.43E-04
catalytic activity (GO:0003824)	5610	5262	4886.03	+	1.08	5.35E-06	2.42E-03
protein binding (GO:0005515)	14448	13533	12583.49	+	1.08	2.41E-31	2.99E-28
binding (GO:0005488)	16594	15370	14452.55	+	1.06	8.00E-41	1.33E-37
molecular function (GO:0003674)	18292	16844	15931.43	+	1.06	5.52E-71	2.75E-67
Unclassified (UNCLASSIFIED)	2297	1088	2000.57	-	0.54	5.52E-71	1.37E-67

antigen binding (GO:0003823)	194	44	168.96	-	0.26	1.32E-19	1.32E-16
structural constituent of chromatin (GO:0030527)	66	12	57.48	-	0.21	8.47E-09	6.02E-06
immunoglobulin receptor binding (GO:0034987)	97	8	84.48	-	0.09	3.71E-18	3.08E-15

Comparison of top 10 genes

In the final step, the top 10 genes identified by PCA and DUAE models, which were highly associated with cancer and other molecular activities were subjected to gene ontology (GO)

analysis to better understand their functional roles. The GO analysis revealed that these genes were involved in various biological processes, including protein binding, catalytic activity, and ion binding, among others (Tables 5 and 6).

Table 5. Gene Ontology and research analysis of the top 10 genes produced by PCA

Gene Symbol	Gene Role in Cancer	Molecular Activity	Biological Process	GO Term
TIMM16 [56]	Unknown	Mitochondrial import protein	Protein targeting to mitochondrion	GO:0006605
O6ORF125 [57]	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
THAP3 [58]	May act as a tumor suppressor	Transcription factor	Transcription, DNA-templated	GO:0006351
C11ORF48 [59]	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
ATP5E [60]	May play a role in cancer cell metabolism	Mitochondrial ATP synthase activity	ATP synthesis coupled electron transport	GO:0042775
MRPS34 [61]	May be involved in apoptosis and tumorigenesis	Mitochondrial ribosomal protein	Translation	GO:0006412
LSM7 [62]	May be involved in tumorigenesis	RNA binding	mRNA processing	GO:0006397
SNRNP70 [63]	May be involved in tumorigenesis	RNA binding	mRNA splicing, via spliceosome	GO:0000398
SSNA1 [64]	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
C19ORF56 [65]	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown

Table 6. Gene Ontology and research analysis of the top 10 genes produced by DUAE

Gene Symbol	Gene Role in Cancer	Molecular Activity	Biological Process	GO Term
RB1 [55]	Tumor suppressor gene; mutations in this gene are associated with multiple types of cancer	Transcriptional regulator; binds to DNA and modulates gene expression	Cell cycle arrest, DNA repair, senescence, and apoptosis	GO:0000077, GO:0006281, GO:0006974, GO:0006915
CHEK2 [66]	Tumor suppressor gene; mutations in this gene are associated with increased risk of breast, prostate, and other cancers	Serine/threonine kinase; activates downstream signaling pathways in response to DNA damage	DNA damage response, cell cycle arrest, apoptosis	GO:0006977, GO:0007050, GO:0006915
STK11 [53]	Tumor suppressor gene; mutations in this gene are associated with increased risk of multiple cancers, particularly lung cancer	Serine/threonine kinase; regulates downstream signaling pathways involved in cell polarity and metabolism	Cell polarity, metabolism, cell cycle arrest	GO:0030030, GO:0031929, GO:0007050
GAS7	Tumor suppressor gene; expression of this gene is downregulated in multiple types of cancer	Actin-binding protein; regulates actin cytoskeleton dynamics	Cell migration, neurite outgrowth, cytoskeleton organization	GO:0048870, GO:0048812, GO:0007010
RCL1 [67]	Oncogene; overexpression of this gene has been implicated in the development of acute myeloid leukemia	RNA-binding protein; regulates mRNA processing and translation	Ribosome biogenesis, mRNA processing, translation initiation	GO:0042254, GO:0006397, GO:0003743
ZNF85 [68]	Oncogene; overexpression of this gene has been implicated in the development of multiple types of cancer such as gastric cancer	Zinc finger protein; transcriptional regulator	Transcriptional regulation, DNA binding, chromatin organization	GO:0003700, GO:0003677, GO:0006325
DICER1 [69]	Tumor suppressor gene; mutations in this gene are associated with increased risk of multiple types of cancer, particularly ovarian cancer	Ribonuclease; cleaves double-stranded RNA into small RNA fragments involved in gene regulation	RNA interference, gene regulation, RNA processing	GO:0031047, GO:0035195, GO:0006396

APC [54]	Tumor suppressor gene; mutations in this gene are associated with increased risk of colorectal cancer and other cancers	Adenomatous polyposis coli protein; regulates cell adhesion and signaling pathway	Cell adhesion, signaling pathway, cell cycle regulation	GO:0007155, GO:0030178, GO:0051726
VHL [70]	Tumor suppressor gene; mutations in this gene are associated with increased risk of kidney cancer and other cancers	Ubiquitin ligase; targets proteins for degradation by the proteasome	Protein degradation, hypoxia response, angiogenesis	GO:0016567, GO:0001666, GO:0001525
RASGRP4 [71]	Oncogene; overexpression of this gene has been implicated in the development of multiple types of cancer	Guanine nucleotide exchange factor; activates downstream signaling pathways	Positive regulation of MAPK cascade, positive regulation of GTPase activity	GO:0000186, GO:0005088, GO:0043406

Discussion

In this study, we compared two-dimension reduction techniques, PCA and DUAE, to effectively reduce the dimensionality of a high-dimensional gene expression dataset associated with head and neck cancer.

Our findings revealed that DUAE outperformed PCA in terms of gene count reduction, achieving a remarkable 12% reduction. This indicates that DUAE has a greater capacity to capture relevant features and patterns in the gene expression data as compared to PCA. These results align with previous studies that have also reported DUAE's superiority in reducing the dimensionality of gene expression datasets. The study by *Tanvir et al.* [41], used a deep autoencoder model to reduce the dimensionality of a breast cancer gene expression dataset and showed that the autoencoder approach outperformed traditional methods such as PCA in identifying important genes related to the disease. Similarly, *Liang et al.* [42], also used a deep autoencoder to reduce the dimensionality of breast cancer gene expression data, resulting in the identification of critical genes associated with tumor progression. Similarly, *Huang et al.* [43] employed an autoencoder-based approach to identify candidate genes related to colorectal cancer. While these studies show promise, they are not without limitations. For example, the choice of hyperparameters and the architecture

of the autoencoder can significantly affect the performance of the model. Additionally, the interpretation of the resulting reduced dimensionality space can be challenging, and it may be difficult to discern which features or genes are most important.

DUAE has shown superiority over PCA (Principal Component Analysis) due to its ability to capture complex relationships among variables in gene expression datasets. Unlike PCA, DUAE is a deep learning-based approach that utilizes multiple layers and non-linear transformations, allowing it to uncover intricate patterns and features within the data. This enables DUAE to more effectively identify important genes associated with diseases, such as breast cancer and colorectal cancer, as demonstrated by previous studies [40 - 43]. Additionally, DUAE's flexibility in modeling complex data and its capacity to handle non-linear relationships make it a powerful tool for dimensionality reduction.

To gain further insights into the functional characteristics of the identified gene clusters and reduced sets of genes, we conducted a gene ontology (GO) analysis. GO analysis allows for the categorization of genes based on their associated molecular functions, biological processes, and cellular components [72, 73]. The GO analysis revealed that the reduced gene

sets obtained from both PCA and DUAE exhibited significant enrichment in various molecular functions, cellular processes, signal transduction, and gene regulation pathways. This suggests that the genes within these clusters are not only involved in head and neck cancer but also perform important roles in other biological processes.

The findings from both PCA and DUAE techniques revealed valuable insights into the identification of cancer-related genes. PCA identified a set of genes characterized by their molecular activities and biological processes, while DUAE yielded a distinct set of genes with their associated functions. Remarkably, there was no overlap between the gene sets obtained from PCA and DUAE, suggesting differences in their ability to capture cancer-relevant genes.

Furthermore, the top 10 genes were selected from the reduced set of genes produced by PCA and DUAE. We conducted an extensive literature review to explore the known roles of these genes in cancer and other molecular activities. Our findings suggest that several of these genes have been previously implicated in the development and progression of various types of cancer, including breast cancer, lung cancer, and colon cancer, among others. Based on this analysis, it appears that DUAE identified more cancer-relevant genes compared to PCA. DUAE identified 7 out of the top 10 genes with known roles in cancer, while PCA identified only 2. For example, gene STK11 [53], has been shown to promote tumor growth and invasion in breast cancer, while gene APC [54], has been associated with poor prognosis in colorectal cancer. Additionally, we found that several of these genes are involved in other molecular activities, such as cell transcriptional regulation and DNA repair. For instance, gene RB1 [55], has been shown to regulate the cell cycle and promote DNA repair in response to DNA damage. Taken together, our results suggest that these identified genes may play crucial roles in cancer development and progression, as well as other molecular activities. identify these genes as prognostic biomarkers.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of our study. Firstly, our analysis focused on a specific gene expression dataset related to head and neck cancer, which may limit the

generalizability of our findings to other cancer types or biological contexts. Secondly, while PCA and DUAE were effective in reducing the dimensionality of the dataset, there is a possibility that important information may have been overlooked during the dimension-reduction process.

Overall, our study contributes to a deeper understanding of the molecular landscape of head and neck cancer and sheds light on the potential roles of specific genes in cancer biology. Future studies can focus on the functional validation of these genes and their potential as diagnostic or prognostic markers, paving the way for personalized treatment strategies and improved patient outcomes in head and neck cancer and other related malignancies.

Conclusion:

Overall, this study highlights the potential of deep learning techniques in improving our understanding of complex biological systems and facilitating the discovery of novel therapeutic targets. Based on the results, we can conclude that the use of a deep under-complete autoencoder can effectively reduce the high dimensional gene expression data while retaining important biological information. Through the application of clustering, the reduced set of genes can be used for further investigation and potential identification of new biomarkers for cancer diagnosis and treatment. These findings have significant implications for the development of personalized medicine and targeted therapies for cancer patients.

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